
Improving Jawi single letters recognizing skills using TNG Techniques for year one students

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Abstract

This research was conducted to overcome the difficulty of pupils in recognizing the Jawi alphabet. The main focus of this research is to improve year one pupils' skills to recognize Jawi alphabet (cha), (nga), (pa), (ga) and (va) and improve the teaching strategy implemented by teachers in the classroom through effective teaching strategies. The "TnG" technique was implemented in this study which emphasizes the use of pictorial dots and colors to achieve the objectives of the study. A total of 6 pupils were selected based on diagnostic tests. The study model of Kemmis and Mc Targgart (1988) was also used as a guide. The data collection methods used were pre and post-test, observations and interviews. The findings of the study showed that the pupils' skill of recognizing the Jawi alphabet increased from 13.3 to 96.7. The research outcome also supported by positive behavior showed by pupils in this research through observation. Meanwhile, the interviews supported the finding that the "TnG" technique used by the teachers enriched pupils' interest in learning Jawi as well as improve pupils' active participation in the classroom. In conclusion, the "TnG" technique effectively improves the skills of recognizing the Jawi alphabet and improving the teaching strategies for Islamic teachers.

Keywords: *recognizing skills, Jawi alphabet, teaching practice, Islamic Education, "TnG" technique.*

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Introduction

The Ministry of Education Malaysia (2015) places great emphasis on the Philosophy of Islamic Education (FPI) to shape the morals and personality of superior students by focusing on seven main areas in the subject of Islamic Education, namely Al-Quran, Hadith, Akidah, Ibadah, Sirah, Adab and Jawi. In general, to achieve the FPI, teachers need to know that the subject of Islamic Education is significant to produce knowledgeable, skilled pupils and practice good values in their daily lives. Islamic education is one of the branches of education that has to impact a student's life. This is because it completely encompasses the physical, spiritual, and moral aspects. The teaching should be understood and appreciated and practiced by the students so that they can adapt to current needs. In the Primary School Standard Curriculum (KSSR), Islamic education is a core subject that must be taught to Muslim students. However, this study is more focused on the problems of students in the field of Jawi. This is because Jawi's field involves fundamental skills such as recognizing hijaiyah letters, spelling, pronunciation, reading and writing Jawi (Asyraf Ridwan and Burhanuddin, 2015). Efforts to strengthen the Jawi field continue to decline when it does not show a significant impact in shaping the generation of Jawi literate. Insufficient mastery of the Jawi field is also the cause of today's generation failing to read the Qur'an well and fluently (Siddiq Fazil, 2008). KPM plays a significant role in maintaining and rejuvenating the Jawi field. Among them, KPM allocates Jawi teaching time starting from the primary school level from year one to year six and is made one of the main focus in the subject of Islamic Education. Therefore, it becomes the main pillar in Islamic Education to master other areas such as Ibadah, Akidah, Sirah and Adab.

Research Objective

Skills in recognizing the Jawi alphabet is one of the problems faced by most students at the primary school level. Pupils face a lot of confusion and difficulty in recognizing Jawi letters. The basis for writing and reading is to be able to know the Jawi letters first. Pupils need to master recognizing the alphabet to join letters becomes words and succeed in creating a complete sentence. Without mastering Jawi writing, recognizing the Jawi alphabet correctly and accurately, students will undoubtedly face difficulties pronouncing the Jawi alphabet according to their form.

To increase the level of mastery and interest of students in Jawi lesson, teachers should be creative and innovative in compiling appropriate techniques to recognize the Jawi alphabet to pronounce, spell, read, and write Jawi. Therefore, this study was conducted to improve the skills of recognizing Jawi alphabet (cha), (nga), (pa), (ga) and (va) using the technique of "TnG" among year one students as well as to describe the practice of pedagogical improvement in improving skills recognize Jawi alphabet (cha), (nga), (pa), (ga) and (va) using the "TnG" technique among first year students.

The study is also divided into five subtopics. Among those that will be discussed are the study's objectives, which describe the focus of this study from general to specific. To support this study, a review of the literature is also revealed to show that this study is critical to study. At the same time, in terms of theory, the researcher will explain the theoretical background used and the methodology used for this study. Discussion for this study will also be described to find out the study's limitations and future research recommendations.

Literature Review

Some students can recognize the Jawi alphabet, but some are still confused and do not know it. Zamri Ibrahim (2009) studied that the students can recognize the Jawi alphabet but they are still weak, let alone connecting the letters even though they have been given a method to write. To increase the level of mastery and interest of students in Jawi, teachers should be creative and innovative in compiling appropriate approaches, strategies, methods and techniques so that students are proficient in recognizing hijaiyah letters, pronunciation, spelling, reading and writing Jawi. J. Williams & Mary Ann (2015) stated that as a teacher must use various teaching methodologies so that the knowledge imparted is easy to be absorbed by the students. This, in turn, makes them active students when teaching and learning take place in the classroom. Jaggil Apak and Suhaimi Taat (2018) stated that teachers who are creative and diversify their teaching methods are factors that influence 21st-century classroom management. Nahar, Safar, Hehsan, & Junaidi (2018), also support that weak in Jawi skills need to be helped through engaging, systematic and effective learning methods. A study by Mardhiyah Md Syamilin (2012) found that the teaching methods contribute to students' weaknesses in mastering the skills of recognizing letters, spelling and reading. According to her,

this happened because there were Islamic Education teachers who used alphabetical writing during class which caused difficulties for students to master the field of Jawi effectively.

However, Gremmen et al. (2016) found that experienced teachers did not necessarily positively impact the teaching and learning session. Mohd Aderi Che Noh et al. (2018) also support that teachers' skills in using accurate and effective teaching methods will enable students' learning process to be more effective and enjoyable. Islamic Education teachers must always be creative and innovative in providing an effective teaching and learning session to help students master the knowledge, skills and values they have learned, especially in Jawi. The weakness in recognizing letters among students was also discussed in the study of Akmariah Mamat and Sofiah Ismail (2010) when students fail to read the Al-Quran because they do not recognize hijaiyah letters. Based on that, Jawi rehabilitation classes are among the methods that can be used to overcome the problem of students recognizing hijaiyah letters. In the study of Muhammad Endut (1990), teaching aids (BBM) in Jawi writing worked insignificance when students have not mastered the skills of reading and writing Jawi causing them to be lousy in the subject of Islamic Education.

Recognizing Jawi alphabet skills was a key to be proficient in Jawi lesson. The visualization technique is a person's ability to build structures mentally (in memory). Even this technique can help fragile and moderate students improve their cognitive abilities (Cambell, Short, and Treinish, 1999). A study by Daud Hamzah (1999) showed that the visualization technique or visualization process is one of the cognitive elements that must be present in students to be more motivated in teaching and learning sessions. Several other studies have also summarized interesting findings. Kamalawati Dolhan, Dyg Putri Awang Mahbi and Yusop Hj Malie (2019) found that the visual representation approach successfully improves students' mastery of literacy skills while poster elements can be used during the teaching and learning process improve student achievement in writing skills (Nornazirah Md Hashim and Jamaludin Bdusah, 2019). Some use posters, pictures, maps and charts to steal the spotlight and make it easier for students to understand the ideas presented. The findings of this study prove those picture elements are essential for use in teaching and learning sessions.

While by using the color method, students will have a visual experience of a human being (Dzulrifli and Mustafar (2013). Other studies also summarize the results of the study, Olurinola and Tayo (2015) found that color can channel information effectively to the cognitive system and humans cause their memory becomes strong while the use of color can stimulate a student's emotions as well as attract their interest (Chang, Xu & Watt, 2018). This proves that the color factor has a positive impact on student learning styles.

Methodology

The research methodology is quantitative and qualitative. Among the instruments used to obtain information and research data are observation instruments, pre and post-tests and interviews. The purpose of the observation instrument conducted was to see the differences in student behavior before and after the intervention was implemented. Pre and post-test were used to collect data quantitatively. To obtain support and data in detail, the interview method was implemented in this study. Based on the results of diagnostic tests, a total of 12 people were selected to be respondents. The action research model used is the Kemmis and Mc Taggart (1988) Model. Based on the model, four steps need to be emphasized. Among them, preliminary survey, action planning, implementation of action and reflection.

Figure 1: Kemmis & Mc Taggart (1988) Action research model

According to Kemmis & Mc Taggart's (1988) model, action research has four stages of development. The first phase is to develop a plan of critically informed action to improve what is already happening. The second phase, to implement what do we plan. The third phase is to observe the effects of the critically informed action in the context in which it occurs. The fourth phase is to reflect on these effects as the basis for further planning, subsequent critically informed action. In other words, if phase four of reflection is found to be unsuccessful, then the same cycle is repeated until the intervention succeeds in overcoming the problem.

Figure 2: Overview Action Research Model

Based on the Kemmis & Mc Taggart (1988) model, the research begins by conducting an initial survey to identify teaching strategies that need to be improved through the experience of conducting teaching and learning in the classroom while being a substitute teacher in the past. For example, I will use my teaching and learning reflection to identify problems that occur and the need to address those problems. Among the problems faced is that some students do not know the Jawi alphabet while writing. In the initial survey process as well, I have made observations in terms of behavior. This is because in Choon Lean Keow (2009), some problems often arise, such as students not paying attention, chatting with friends, and postponing the work given by the teacher. So, I have prepared a behavioral checklist for use in this study. After identifying the problem, an appropriate action plan has been planned to overcome the problem that I use 'TnG' as an intervention. At the next stage, I have implemented the action using the planned intervention by first explaining how to use 'TnG'. When they use it, I will observe and collect data in terms of behavior. With the data I have obtained, I will reflect on the effectiveness of the intervention thus referring to the objectives of

my study. The purpose of the reflection was to identify whether the interventions used successfully overcame the problems encountered or needed improvement to continue the action for the second cycle.

Figure 3: An overview of the Study Model circle

Findings

Data obtained from observation instruments, pre and post-tests and interviews were analyzed. The following paragraph will discuss the results of the analysis of the instruments used.

Based on figure 2, there is an improvement in the skills of recognizing single Jawi letters (cha), (nga), (pa), (ga) and (va) using the "TnG" technique. Data were obtained as a result of pre- and post-tests conducted in the classroom.

Figure 2: Difference of Pre and Post Test scores

The study results found an increase in scores in the post-test compared to the pre-test after the "TnG" technique was applied. This can be seen through the total marks for the pre-test of 80 marks while for the post-test, it is 580 marks. The total marks found a significant increase of 500 marks. For respondent 5, has shown an increase in the highest score of 100% from 0% in the pre-test to 100% in the post test. Meanwhile, the lowest increase was 80% of study 3 respondents which increased from 0% in the pre-test to 80%. The results of the analysis of the study can be concluded that the method of "TnG" can improve pupils' performance in the skills of recognizing single Jawi letters (cha), (nga), (pa), (ga) and (va). This is because the "TnG" method applied through hands-on learning has made pupils actively involved in the classroom, thus attracting students to color the letters during the teaching and learning session.

Table 1

Comparison of observations before and after the intervention was applied.

No.	Behavior	Before		After		Comparison	
		Number of respondents	(%)	Number of respondents	(%)	Number of respondents	(%)
1	The pupils are unable to pay attention during the teaching and learning session	4	66.7	0	0	-4	-66.7
2	The pupils yawn during teaching and learning session	2	33.3	0	0	-2	-33.3
3	The pupils chatting with their friends that sit next to them	5	83.3	1	16.7	-4	-66.7
4	The pupils do not complete the exercises which the teacher gives	5	83.3	0	0	-5	-83.3
5	The pupils draw during teaching and learning session	4	66.7	1	16.7	-3	-50
6	The pupils give cooperation when they are carrying out the activity	2	33.3	6	100	+4	+66.7
7	The pupils are happy during the teaching and learning sessions.	0	0	6	100	+6	+100
8	The pupils often annoy a friend next door	3	50	1	16.7	2	-33.3
9	The pupils do other subject homework.	4	66.7	0	0	-4	-66.7
10	The pupils always look outside the class during the teaching and learning session	3	50	1	16.7	-2	-33.3

Data collection on how teachers improve pedagogical practices was also analyzed using observation and interview methods.

Referring to table 1, initially, the study respondents showed no interest in focusing and learning to recognize jawi alphabet. For behavior "The pupils chatting with their friends that sit next to them" has shown 83.3 percent which five respondents get involved. After using the "TnG" technique, only one respondent behaved in such a way with 16.7 percent. "The pupils are happy during the teaching and learning session" showed 0 percent but after the intervention was implemented 100 percent that is a total of six respondents, were happy with the teaching and learning session. In general, the study's findings found that all students' behaviors clearly show that they are very interested in learning to recognize the Jawi alphabet because of the teacher's exciting teaching methods. This is evidenced when students exhibit positive behaviors during teaching and learning sessions. The "TnG" intervention has made the students interested and fun to connect the dots set and color

the letters and pictures according to the guidelines provided. In addition to the students having fun coloring, they also understand and remember Jawi alphabet and objects that are commonly heard and are around them.

As a result of the interview analysis, I used content analysis by re-reading the interview transcript and marking the critical content. After that, I identified the themes found on the interview transcript. Content analysis for the interview transcript can be referenced in figure 5 below:

Figure 5: Analysis of Interview Transcripts with respondents

The impact, various teaching methods and improvement from time to time can be seen through students' mastery in the knowledge and skills taught. Interestingly, the teachers interviewed agreed that the "TnG" intervention had complemented and improved teachers' pedagogical practices in improving the skills of recognizing single Jawi letters. Among other similar themes frequently mentioned by the teachers interviewed was color. The analysis for interview transcripts for other themes can be referenced in figure 6 below:

Figure 6: Analysis of Color Theme Interview Transcripts

Limitation and Future Research

Limitation

In the early stages, students successfully improve their skills in recognizing single Jawi letters using the 'TnG' technique and it can be expanded to a broader scope. Therefore, this study needs to overcome and improve on two things. First, the limitation on places in one state, namely Johor. Secondly, the study was limited when implemented at Sekolah Kebangsaan Temenggong Abdul Rahman 2 (STAR2). Third, limitations on year one students who are seven years old.

Future research

This research shows a significant impact on the respondent. TNG technique proves that it can make Jawi lesson more exciting and fun and helps the teacher to deliver their lesson effectively. Moreover, the pupils feel enjoyable and will actively participate in classroom activities. By using TNG technique, pupils in the classroom show positive behavior towards teachers and friends. In terms of recognizing Jawi Alphabet, the respondents manage to remember the Jawi alphabet clearly. TNG technique is an excellent intervention to help pupils recognize and remember the Jawi alphabet easily by connecting the dots into the alphabet and pictures.

In the interest of the education of the next generation, this study needs to be continued. The weaknesses identified need to be improved from time to time to improve the effectiveness and quality of the study to be conducted. Among the improvements that can be implemented is that researchers can use single Jawi alphabet with different objects. Using color, the researcher can also determine the appropriate color for the letters and

objects set. Further, this intervention can be improved by incorporating it into Jawi modules according to the diversification of teaching and learning methods and techniques in the subject of Islamic Education for Jawi.

The study findings from the instruments used such as pre-test and post-test are very much needed for future researchers so that they can get an initial picture before implementing it. The data obtained from the interviews are beneficial for the following study which consists of the same variables. However, for further study the researcher can use instruments such as field notes and worksheets to support the study's findings. Researchers can also expand the scope by focusing on spelling, writing and reading skills in the field of Jawi. Limitations of the study can also be applied to students in different years and levels in order to be able to see their mastery and understanding of the field of Jawi.

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